

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

WP7

Dissemination and Communication Plan

Deliverable 7.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan

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1. Introduction

SECURE Work Package 7 (WP7) Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1) – is an internal project document describing the actions and tools for the promotion of the project and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences, including the media and the public, in a strategic, coherent and effective manner. It offers a comprehensive communication strategy, including objectives of communication, which will raise the awareness of the project and disseminate project goals, progress, and final results to target stakeholders who can directly benefit from the project, and distribute the information to the wider public.

Dissemination and Communication Plan establishes the basis for the development of a common dissemination and communication action during the project. This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in SECURE project, designated as public regarding the dissemination level. The deliverable is alive and will be modified according to the project needs during project's duration. This deliverable will periodically update the strategies of the project as well as identify in detail the stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, KPIs and procedures agreed.

The effects of the dissemination activities will be monitored and evaluated by the work package leader and project partners periodically and modified accordingly. The results of the strategies implemented will be made visible at the end of project activities in the Final Dissemination, Communications & Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

2. About the SECURE project

The Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework (RCF) that offers a set of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity.

During its two-year duration, the project consortium will develop, produce and launch:

- **State-of-the-art on Research Careers (WP1)** – Conduct a state-of-the-art on literature, recommendations on research careers and on best practice examples of tenure track-like models.
- **SECURE Research Career Framework (WP2)** – Develop a comprehensive Research Career Framework integrating relevant existing policies. Engage research stakeholders to co-design and validate the Research Career Framework.
- **Tenure Track-Like Models (WP3)** – Develop a range of tenure track-like models integrating best practices from existing use cases. Engage research stakeholders to co-design and validate the Tenure Track-Like Models.
- **Implementing and trialing the Research Career Framework (WP4)** – Conduct trials at organisations to implement, test, and refine the Research Career Framework.
- **Mainstreaming the Research Career Framework (WP5)** – Mainstream the Research Career Framework through EURAXESS, develop policy briefs, and organize a final summit and policy roundtable.
- **Coordination and Data Management (WP6)** - Develop framework covering standardization of approach, data collection, methodology and analysis

- **Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (WP7)** - develop D&C plan and Exploitation plan. Build a project identity with dedicated communication channels and formats. Raise awareness about SECURE and disseminate and exploit the outputs and results of SECURE to target stakeholders and the wider public.

More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.

3. Project Impact

Research Career Framework and Tenure Track-like Models as the main project outputs are connected, both in implementation and impact. Both are expected to be major undertakings with an impact spreading over the duration of the project (24 months). Medium impact (up to 5 years after the project end) and long-term (up to 20 years after the project ends) impact is expected and projected as follows:

- Impact through creating the RCF as a common researchers' career structure, recognising the diversification of careers, interinstitutional, international and intersectoral mobility, and competences gained and needed by PhD candidates and postdocs within and outside academia, building on existing best practices and linked to ESCO, Charter & Code, the new European Researcher Competency Framework and recent Council Recommendations.
- Impact through developing new Tenure Track-Like models improving career development and reducing precarity in academia, including requirements for professional development and career progression at particular career transition points as well as recommendations on intersectoral mobility and involving the non-academic sector from the onset in training and career development of PhD candidates.
- Mainstreaming the RCF and TTL models through practical examples of successful trials, responding to stakeholder feedback, extensive consultation and dissemination activities and embedding within the EURAXESS network including the service centres, newly-established EURAXESS talent management hubs, and the ERA Talent Platform that is currently being developed. Project partner BZN will be leading this activity.

Communication and Dissemination activities will support the better acceptance of Research Career Framework and Tenure track-like models, both in the research community and the wider social community. More about impact figures can be found in the project grant agreement.

4. WP 7 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation is an important part of the Horizon Europe projects that all partners must take part in. Communicating European projects should aim at how research and innovation are contributing to an “Innovation Union”. This objective is divided into two complementary activities:

Dissemination and communication activities oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders identified, parties concerned both individual researchers and institutions, journalists and general public. Dissemination and communication activities will be described in this document (D7.1).

Exploitation actions will establish the main pillars for a future uptake plan of the most promising and mature results generated in the project. The exploitation strategy will identify technical choices towards the most promising directions, thus maximizing the opportunities for innovation and further development and usage of the project results. Exploitation actions will be described in the separate deliverable, the Exploitation Plan (D7.2).

Main objective of the work package 7 is to support the previous packages and through appropriate strategic measures diffuse and propagate the project goals, progress, results in order to reach target audiences and wider public, thus provide visibility of project aims and actions. The aim is to communicate with and reach out to relevant stakeholder groups and a wider public, and to inform about the use and benefits of the project for them. Subsequently, the goal is to stimulate further initiatives that can lead to the wider impact beyond the scope of the project. The general goal for this project is to bring forth scientific, techno-economic and societal impact in the field of research careers, overcoming precarity and inciting new approaches in order to support and evolve more sustainable careers.

Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN) is the leader of the work package seven and its activities, along with the support of all project partners and their channels in dissemination of project results. Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Committee is established for planning and coordinating these activities and will be meeting monthly, every second week of the month, on Thursday at 11am CEST. The Committee consists of the SECURE project WP leaders, namely CPN, ICoRSA, PLOCAN, TGB, Vitae and EurSc. The Committee is responsible for developing a focused strategy on how to promote the project and its results. The activities are carried out throughout the duration of the project.

Work package 7 related materials and resources can be accessed [here](#) .

4.1 Objectives, Target Groups and Key Messages of WP7

The main objective of the communication is to reach out and communicate with the society, and inform about the use and benefits of the project for citizens. The main dissemination objectives are to build relationships with key stakeholders and networks, main ones including:

- Universities and their associations (i.e., EUA, LERU, Guild, Coimbra Group)
- research performing organisations (RPO) and their associations, (i.e., Science Europe)
- research financing organisations (RFO) and their associations,
- Policy stakeholders (i.e., OECD, UNESCO, EC, Ministries)

- non-governmental organisations (NGO),
- governmental organisations (GO),
- relevant organisations employing researchers
- individual researchers, research professionals and others
- industry and companies all in order to
- encourage active participation in the project activities,
- share resources,
- exchange knowledge and
- bring about active synergies and collaborations

and raise awareness about the project results and outputs, their benefits, use and applicability, ensuring their support and participation.

Work package 7 will build relationships with key stakeholders and networks. The primary target groups are research performing organisations (Universities and research institutes) research financing organisations, and researchers themselves — actively engaged either by being a partner in the project consortium, through direct participation or through various networks.

Certain emphasis is on the policy makers at all levels, on their support and the impact they can generate. Policy makers and societal actors are active recipients and are informed on project activities and outcomes, and successfully engaging with policy makers fosters a better follow-up of the project’s outcome.

Table 1: Dissemination and Communication — primary target groups

Target audiences	Audiences segmentation	Communication channels
Internal consortium	18 organisations participating in the project, including pilots	Email and other internal communication tools, events
Pilot Research Performing Organisations (RPO)	RPO participatinc in SECURE: PLOCAN, UCY, UNIRI, and UNL	Email, Direct meetings, Events, Social Media, Newsletter, Publications, Website
Pilot Research Fundin Organisations (RFO)	RFOs participating in SECURE: UEF	Email, Direct meetings, Events, Social Media, Newsletter
All other RPOs and RFOs	Organisations connected to the project partner networks, and researchers, in the long term Researchers in RPOs	Email, Direct meetings, Events, Social Media, Newsletter, Publications, Website

Universities	Management and Unirepresentatives, HR units (with the help of EUA, Coimbra Group, ISE etc.)	Surveys, Publications, Policy Briefs, Emails, Social Media, Newsletter, Website
Pilot recruitment agency	Recruitment agency participating in SECURE: ADOC	Email, Direct meetings, Events, Social Media, Newsletter
Researchers, Scientific community, industry	Researchers, permanent academics doing research, scientists and policy makers across Europe and beyond.	Email, Direct meetings, Events, Social Media, Newsletter, Publications, Website
Policy makers	Policy stakeholders (OECD, UNESCO, EC, Ministries)	Policy Briefs and Press releases, Specific Email campaign and Events, Social Media, Newsletter, Publications, Website

Wider secondary target groups are the societal and economic actors such as citizens, public organisations, industry and civil society organisations, especially ones relating to SECURE topics, as valuable mediators that can help the project’s promotion and involvement in the existing communities.

Table 2: Dissemination and Communication — secondary target groups

Target audiences	Audience segmentation	Communication channels
Research and Innovation institutions and organisations	Research and Innovation hubs, knowledge transfer agencies, regional networks	Direct Email, Direct meetings, Email campaigns through Newsletter, Direct messages through LinkedIn
Universities and think tanks dealing with research and innovation (policy) issues	Researchers from universities, Think-tanks staff dealing with research and innovation (policy) issues	Direct Email, Direct meetings, research departments online community, Email campaigns through Newsletter, Direct messages through LinkedIn
Industry associations	Research staff associations, Research support organisations, representatives who deal with research and innovation issues (framework conditions, technological developments) and other organisations reached via project partners	Direct Email, Direct meetings, community groups, Email campaigns through Newsletter, Direct messages through LinkedIn
Other relevant EC projects, coalitions and interest groups (experts and others)	For example OPUS project and similar initiatives, networks, and organisations	Website and social media, events, webinars, newsletters etc.

In the communication and dissemination, key messages are used as slogans and headlines to inspire and guide initial dissemination and communication activities and catch the attention of the target audiences. Slogan as a short version of the key messages is developed for use on the web, in the promotion and other visual materials that will be used during the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities.

Some of the initial SECURE slogans are:

- SECURE – Sustainable careers for researcher empowerment
- SECURE – Improving researchers careers and reducing career precarity

Additional messages will be developed during the scope of the project and along with social media hashtags will attract the wider public.

4.2 Tools for Communication and Dissemination

In order to achieve the communication and dissemination goals, the following tools will be developed and used:

4.2.1 Website

An official project webpage will be developed and managed throughout the duration of the project. Website is the main communication and dissemination tool. It explains the project and its timeline to a wider audience. It is user-friendly and presents the project in a non-technical language. Separate page sections will be dedicated to the project results – objectives and deliverables, with the possibility for the project outputs to be viewed, extracted and downloaded. The news section of the website will provide latest updates of the project via project social media pages and official announcements.

Project website will be promoted via social media, partner networks, scientific and research organisations, as well as at the various events in order to increase organic traffic. The website impact will be measured by the KPI that is the number of unique visits per month. The initial expected number of visits is 750, starting from the month six, and with the expected increase at the end. The total website impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24). The official website can be found at <https://secureproject.eu/>.

4.2.2 Social media

The official SECURE social media accounts will be set up, namely on Twitter and LinkedIn, as those are the channels research professionals and research-related organisations use the most. Twitter offers the opportunity to connect with an active academic, research and science community via discussion and promotion of project-related topics. Twitter will be used for regular posting, promotion via trending hashtags (#research, #researchers, #researchcareers, #precarity, #openscience, #researchculture and other), and tweeting from events. LinkedIn offers the opportunity to present and share with the community professionals and build connections with a wider network of policy makers at all levels. LinkedIn will be used for disseminating main project outputs (such as project methodology, research career framework, surveys and other). Project social media is regularly updated throughout the project duration.

Main KPIs regarding social media activities will be the number of followers and posts. Five hundred followers and 100 posts are expected per project year (1000 followers and at least 200 posts for the duration of the project). Where needed, the paid promotion on social media will be used to boost and improve the visibility and impact. The total social media impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24). The official SECURE social media account can be found at https://twitter.com/secure_eu and <https://www.linkedin.com/company/90798848/>

4.2.3 Factsheets and Infographics

A number of non-tech factsheets and infographics will be produced to inform the public and different non-expert audiences outside of the project's own community. This attractive informative material will be designed according to project's visual identity and present research careers' topics and project highlights in a visually pleasing and easily accessible way. It will be reviewed and updated accordingly.

Factsheets will be shared via official project website, social media and used by partners at events for presentation purposes and shared via partner networks. At least two factsheets will be produced, with the KPI of 400 shares or downloads. Additional informative material will be produced at the end of SECURE with final results. The total factsheet impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

4.2.4 Conference Attendance and Presentations

An official presentation of the project will be created to be used by all partners for promotional purposes. Work package seven will identify and attend relevant events for promotion and dissemination. Project partners will be actively engaged in promoting and presenting the project at relevant online and in-person events throughout the duration of the project. Such events will serve for the dissemination of the scientific work of this project in the academic, research and science professional communities.

Project partners will take part in a minimum of ten conferences / presentations of the project. Project partners will map the conferences / events in 2023 and 2024 with the highest exposure, and certain importance will be given to the participation in events after the first project outputs are released, in order to make the biggest impact of the published results. The conferences/events participation list is open for changes and is updated accordingly, and it can be reached [here](#). The total conferences impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

4.2.5 Media and Press Releases

Media and press releases will be issued when appropriate, often in tandem with the project's participation at conferences to maximise the exposure and publicity of the project and the Research Career Framework as one of the main outputs of the project. Work package 7 will work with media departments of partner organisations to exploit the existing contacts in order to get more exposure. Other media pieces such as interviews, articles and blog entries on research topics and similar will be implemented when appropriate. There will be three interview sessions – initial one, after the first year, and final one. All these outputs will be placed on a project website as well and promoted via project social media. Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity that is expected to have a major media impact, the project partners will inform the granting authority. The total media and press release impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

4.2.6 Publications

Partners will collaboratively produce publications, papers and reports linked to the work packages 1-5. These outputs will be produced in accordance with the open science principles and publications will be released in the open access journals. A minimum of ten publications will be released during two years, out of which two at least in the peer-reviewed scientific journals. Project will publish the Policy Brief as well, Initial Policy Brief (M9) and Policy Brief (M21). The total publications impact will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

4.3 Visual Identity

Work package seven is responsible for developing an appealing, modern and distinct visual identity that will rely information about SECURE project in an approachable, non-tech, easily digestible way. For the purpose of this project, an official logo, font, and visual materials will be produced and used for all the project's promotional materials including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., both in electronic form, via traditional or social media. According to visual identity, templates for documents, reports and presentations will be made. Additionally, all public appearances of the project, the official EU emblem flag and the following funding statement will be used:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

SECURE

Sustainable Careers for
Researcher Empowerment

Typography

Calibre Semi Bold
Calibre Medium
 Calibre Regular
 Calibre Light

CALIBRE
 Basic font

Website Fonts

INTER SEMI BOLD
INTER REGULAR

INTER
 Basic font

Figures 1-4: SECURE visual identity — banner, logo, color scheme and typography.

Complete visual identity will be presented in more detail in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24). Visual identity materials can be accessed [here](#) and consulted on the official project website <https://secureproject.eu/>.

4.4 Additional Communication and Dissemination Tools

To support the communication activities and reach dissemination goals, additional tools will be used:

- **Project one-pager & flyer** – will be made to promote the project in scientific and research organisations and networks, as well as at the relevant events. Via an email campaign and giving out flyers at relevant events, a one-pager will invite the stakeholders to explore and spread the news about the project further.
- **Annual survey** – project partner’s ICoRSA annual survey will be tailored to validate SECURE impact figures. The target of two thousand completed surveys is planned, at least one thousand per project year.
- **Closing summit** – near the project’s end, a final event will be organized for relevant stakeholders and a wider public in order to present project results, and to further promote research career framework and tenure track-like models. This event will be planned with the aim to widen the impact and influence. The expected participation is two hundred people minimum, with even more expected to join virtually.
- **Policy roundtable** – near the project’s end, the final summit will be organized for relevant stakeholders and wider public in order to present and promote the policy briefs, RCF and other project outcomes.
- **Pilot hubs and networks** – Dissemination activities will be embedding within the EURAXESS network including the service centres, newly-established EURAXESS talent management hubs, and the ERA Talent Platform that is currently being developed. Project partner BZN leads the hubs focusing on talent management which will serve as contact point for dissemination and provide a channel for two-way communication, together with ERA talent platform and network of 605 service centers. Project partner Vitae will support regional talent management hubs in the UK. Other established national and local hubs will be scaled up during the project’s duration.

4.5 Internal Communication

Internal project partner communication will be led by the work package six leader PLOCAN and does not enter the scope of this plan. Work package six will ensure the management, coordination, and internal communication of the project. Communication between the consortium and the EU will go via project manager PLOCAN and the EU project officer.

Regular monthly dissemination and communication committee meetings will be led by work package seven leader CPN. Committee partners (CPN, ICoRSA, Plocan, TGB, and Vitae) will be meeting monthly, every second week of the month, on Thursday at 11am CEST.

Work package seven will additionally provide organizational support for internal meetings, internal or external events, workshops, both in physical and online or hybrid – such as kickoff meeting, closing summit, policy roundtable, trials. The support includes communication regarding securing venues, travel, catering, travel costs reimbursement, as well as technical support for online platforms.

Figure 5: Dissemination and Communication organizational chart

5. Table overview of WP7 KPIs

For the event and continuous flow of communication and dissemination activities, in the table below are given the average targets per month or year. These figures are subject to modification according with the continuous project activities and the average impact.

Tools	KPIs	Total targets	Average targets	Strategy
Website	Website visits	18 000 unique visits	750 per month starting from M6 with expected increase near the end of project	Promoted via social media, partner networks and media and press releases and events.
Social Media	Number of posts and followers	200+ and 1000+ followers	100 posts per year and 500 followers per year; 9 posts per	Twitter and LinkedIn will be made to promote

			month and 42 followers per month on average	the project, will be actively updated and focused onto forming a diverse community of relevant stakeholders.
Factsheets	Number of shares/downloads	Minimum of 2 factsheets and minimum of 400 shares/downloads	Average of 200 per year	Will be published on the project website and social media. Partners will use them on events/conferences to further promote the project
Presentations	Number of presentations at conferences/events	Minimum 10 presentations	Average of 5 per year	Project partners will be actively engaged in scientific dissemination of their work. The list of opportunities for conference/event presentation will be gathered on project Sharepoint.
Publications	Number of publications	Minimum 10 publications, minimum 2 in peer-reviewed scientific journals; Policy Brief	Average of 5 per year	Project partners will be actively engaged in scientific dissemination of their work. Reports and papers linked to work packages 1-5 will be published by the principles of open science in relevant journals. The list of opportunities for publication will be gathered on project Sharepoint.
Press releases	Number of press releases	Minimum 10 press releases	/	Issuing media releases and working with media departments of partner

				organisations to promote the project. The list of opportunities for promotion will be gathered on project Sharepoint.
Survey	Number of responses	Minimum 2000 responses	1000 completed responses per year on average	Promoted via website and social media, partner networks and media and press releases.
Closing summit	Number of participants	200 participants (in person or hybrid/online)	/	Promoted via website and social media, partner networks and media and press releases.
Overall project reach	Number of researchers reached	50 000 researchers reached (overall estimated total reach for all activities)	Around 25000 researchers per year, 2000+ per month on average. Expected increase at the end of project.	Using partners' points of contact and other network associations (such as MSCA, ERC, ISC, ISE, UNESCO) to boost the visibility and reach of project activities and results.

Additional tools may be implemented, such as interviews, online events, blog posts, posters and similar. The working data will be kept updated on the project's Sharepoint monthly or bi-monthly and can be accessed on the project Sharepoint. The total impact of activities will be presented in the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Report (D7.3) due in the month 24.

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

WP7

Dissemination and Communication Plan

SECURE PROJECT

IF YOU WOULD LIKE TO KNOW MORE ABOUT
OUR PROJECT ACTIVITIES

E-MAIL US info@secureproject.eu

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